

Actual vs Predicted (SunHoursMax)

Standardized Residuals (SunHoursMax)

Partial Regression Plot (SunHoursMax)

Durbin-Watson Statistic

$$DW = 1.2368$$

Interpretation:

1 = positive autocorrelation

2 = no autocorrelation

4 = negative autocorrelation

Breusch–Pagan Test

LM Statistic: 4.4393

p-value: 0.0351

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

White Test

White Statistic: 13.8378

df: 2

p-value: 0.0010

Conclusion: Heteroskedasticity Exists

Histogram of Residuals (SunHoursMax)

P-P Plot (Normality Test) – SunHoursMax

